

ATLAS is a scientific research project involving people from across Europe, the USA and Canada. It is the biggest ever research project trying to find out more about life in the deep Atlantic Ocean.

ATLAS scientists are trying to answer these questions:

What lives there?

What are they doing?

How are they connected to other areas?

What effect could a changing ocean have on them?

Will we find the same, similar or different life in other deep ocean areas?

The answers to these questions will help ATLAS scientists give advice to governments, businesses and other scientists on the best ways to protect the deep-sea ecosystems from issues such as climate change, pollution and certain fishing techniques.

This knowledge will also support sustainable growth in jobs and companies that rely on the sea.